

Head of Schools' Experiences in Managing Teenage Mothers in Secondary School Education: A Case Study of Dar es Salaam Region, Tanzania

Hasan Manyama,¹ & Honoratha M. Mushi, PhD.²

¹Department of Education, Faculty of Education and Legal Studies,
Kampala International University in Tanzania, Dar es Salaam, Tanzania.
Corresponding author. Email: manyamahasan@gmail.com

²Department of Education, Faculty of Education and Legal Studies,
Kampala International University in Tanzania, Dar es Salaam, Tanzania.
Email: honorathamushi@gmail.com

Abstract:

This qualitative study explored the experiences of secondary school heads in managing teenage mothers in five districts of the Dar es Salaam Region in Tanzania. A phenomenological research design was employed, using descriptive statistics within the qualitative paradigm. The specific objectives were to explore heads of secondary schools' experiences in managing teenage mothers in their schools; examine the strategies employed by heads of schools in managing and supporting teenage mothers in schools; identify the challenges that the heads of secondary schools encountered and how the challenges identified were address. A sample of 74 respondents, including heads of secondary schools' teacher coordinators, classroom teachers, teenage mothers, and district or regional education officers were interviewed, engaged in focus group discussions (FGD), and were observed as they engaged themselves in their day-to-day work activities. Thematic analysis that was used was guided by transformational and servant-leadership theoretical principles. The findings indicated that heads of schools lacked appropriate training, knowledge and experiences necessary for effective management of schooling teenage mothers. The study revealed that heads of schools employed strategies such as guidance and counseling services, academic support services, and parenting life skills education to support the teenage mothers. The study recommends that the government establishes schools that are accommodating to teenage mothers, have on-site child care facilities and child care staff, provide training and professional development for heads of schools and teachers, ensure adequate resources, effective support systems, and teacher motivation.

Keywords: Motivation, Secondary Schools, Teenage Mothers, Training, Tanzania.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Heads of schools have, in most cases, been considered second parents and leaders of all learners in their schools since they are responsible for the well-being of the learners during school hours (Ngabaza & Shefer, 2013). For example, they are to a significant extent, responsible to guarantee learners' wellbeing in terms of physical, emotional, quality academic delivery, financial assistance, safety and security. Despite limited expertise in managing and counseling teenage mothers (Makiwane & Udjo, 2006), heads of secondary schools that enroll teenage mothers are obliged to manage both teenage mothers and other students in the schools.

As a consequence of the conditions narrated above, heads of secondary schools are faced with challenges as they manage teenage mothers in their school contexts. Limited heads of secondary schools' knowledge and skills regarding effective management of teenage mother is considered in relation to their pre-service training in teacher colleges. Teachers' pre-service training curriculum does not adequately prepare them; in addition, the heads of secondary schools have insufficient time to deal with schooling teenage mothers. A study conducted by Bhana et al., (2010) found that pregnant students need support and encouragement from the heads of their schools and teachers. It is however unfortunate some of the heads of school consider schooling teenage mothers as a problem and a private matter and thus none of their problems.

Ngabaza & Shefer, (2013) argue that although heads of schools were not adequately trained to deal with teenage mothers at teachers' colleges, and their schools lacked appropriate programs and the capacity to support such learners, they generally concern themselves with the safety of the teenage mothers in their schools.

Apart from the historical perspective concerning heads of schools' experiences in managing teenage mothers in secondary schools, this section explores the historical perspective of teenage mothers in secondary school. Teenage mothers refer to a state or condition wherein girls aged 9-19 years get pregnant and have to take the responsibility of mothering their children (WHO, 2018). When this condition occurs for schooling girls, the teenage mothers' lives change significantly. Their educational progress and career dreams either get permanently curtailed or somehow interfered and diminished. Generally, teenage mothers' lives become vulnerable to poverty and discriminated. Most often, their health and the health of their off springs suffer; their education is likely to come to an end. They are most likely end up not being able to attain the employment of their interest or choice and their originally projected timelines for getting employment is generally extended.

In most cases, teenage mothers end up in cohorts of young girls with minimum education and mothers with limited economic opportunities. Under such conditions, teenage schooling mothers ultimately become future grown up women who remain incapable of contributing fully to the development of their families, communities and countries (UNFPA, 2018).

Adolescent pregnancies pose substantial risks and encounters for young girls' increased risks of maternal and child mortality, limited educational opportunities, and

continuation of poverty cycles (UNFPA, 2018). Teenage mothers constitute one of the major social problems with negative effects on society. Generally, adolescent pregnancies do not support the development of girl children, especially in the academic arena. This is caused by the target girls' low ages and the limited social and economic support for the girls and their children. Both teenage mothers and their children need sustained support, particularly when the teenage mother needs to continue with education as well as take good care of their children (Gyan, 2013).

1.1 Objective of the study

The general objective of this study is to explore heads of secondary schools' experiences in managing teenage mothers in secondary schools in Dar es Salaam Region, Tanzania.

1.2 Research questions

This research process was guided by the following research questions that were generated from the research objectives as highlighted in section 1.1

- i. Do the heads of schools' have expected experiences in managing teenage mothers in their secondary schools?
- ii. What strategies do heads of school's employ to manage and support teenage mothers in secondary schools?
- iii. What challenges do heads of secondary schools' encounter in addressing the needs of teenage mothers in secondary school (and how are the challenges addressed?)

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual review

Heads of schools' experiences was considered as an independent variable and was discussed under the domains of knowledge, skills, and the length of service of the head of school, which served as the leader. On the other hand, the researchers assigned the overall practices of "Managing Teenage mothers at school" to be a dependent variable, where the outcomes were assessed by considering the positive or negative perceptions among teachers, parents, and students (including time scheduling for breastfeeding and attending health clinic services) towards the schooling of teenage mothers. Between the interactions of these two main variables, the researchers delimited the so-called intervening variables to include school support (such as counseling and guidance services), education policy, culture, and cooperation among education stakeholders.

2.2 Empirical review

Little research has been done on heads of schools serving as teenage mothers ' primary caregivers while they are in school. Even in cases when heads of schools provide support and guidance to teenage mothers, Bhana et al., (2010) note that many of these interactions will probably be "judgmental and moralistic" in nature. The key factors

influencing the heads of schools' experiences in managing teenage mothers were found to be "teachers' attitudes and practices" in a study conducted by Bhana et al., (2010) on South African teachers' responses to teenage pregnancy and teenage mothers in schools. Morrell, (2011) contends, however, that heads of schools shouldn't be seen as morally reprehensible people. For their unfavorable opinions of teenage mothers, given those teachers' reactions to them are "also shaped by their social and cultural context." The results of Bhana and Ngabaza, (2012), who concentrated their study on life orientation teachers and guidance counselors, further affirm the impact of culture on teachers' responses.

According to a different study conducted by Haufiku, (2014) on the inclusion policy of teenage mothers, it is clear that some of the heads of schools lack basic abilities and experiences since they are unable to help them manage their multiple obligations. According to the survey, pregnant students were not given the support and attention they needed while attending class. Due to this disregard for adolescent mothering, correlates with the findings of Ngabaza & Shefer, (2013), who suggested that "teachers should be trained in supportive measures, and guidance on dealing with pregnant learners should be made available. "It seems that "schools probably do not have the resources and have too many other demands to give this issue any attention."

2.3 Theoretical framework

Considering heads of schools' experience's in managing teenage mothers, it becomes necessary that different theories will have to be brought into use in order to explain the issue of managing teenage mothers in Dar es Salaam secondary schools. Teenage mothers constitute a unique phenomenon in education particularly in primary and secondary education the 'victims' are at a very young age. Different scholars at different times have described their perceptions regarding heads of schools, experiences in managing teenage mothers. Some of such descriptions include theoretical framework. Greenleaf (1970) explores servant-leadership theory that prioritizes the well-being and empowerment of employees a group which include among others, heads of secondary schools, teacher, and educational officers. Transformational leadership theory by James McGregor Burns, the theory focuses on the role of a leader in inspiring and motivating followers to achieve exceptional performance and to transcend their own self-interest for the good of the organization or society.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employed a phenomenological research design accompanied by qualitative research approach were all integrated together to provide clear presentation of the research problem. In the case of targeted population; the targeted population for this study covers all heads of schools, teenage mothers, and teachers, include coordinator teachers and District Education Officers of those districts with enrolled teen mothers within in Dar-es-salaam Region.

3.1 Sample size and sampling procedure

The sampling technique that utilized in this study is known as purposive sampling. This approach involves deliberately selecting individuals based on the specific purpose that aligns with particular qualities relevant to the investigation theme and their significance. This study purposively selected categories of respondents such as teenage mothers, 1education officers from each District, 1Teachers' coordinators from each school, and 1heads of secondary schools from each school special for teacher mother from the Dar es Salaam region to obtain their firsthand experiences on dealing with and managing teenage mothers in secondary schools from their time of pregnancy, bearing their children to be re-enrolled again into the formal education system.

3.2 Instrumentation

For data collection, the researcher intended to utilize two different instruments for collecting data, namely primary and secondary data collection methods. Primary data refers to the new information developed or directly obtained by a researcher from specifically sampled items/participants from the target field (Cohen et al., 2007). For purposes of this study, interview, focus group discussion (FGD), and observation checklist were used, the combination of these data collection methods was considered essential to triangulate data so as to ensure the authenticity of the data collected. Triangulation ensures consistency, efficiency, accurate, and reliability in research data collection.

3.3 Reliability and validity of data

Saunders et al. (2019) emphasize that in research design, reliability and validity are primary factors of quality control. Reliability ensures consistent and dependable research methods, while validity reflects the extent to which the study accurately measures the intended concepts. Upholding both reliability and validity is essential for producing credible and impactful research that can withstand scrutiny and advance scholarly knowledge. Reliability the researcher solicited a group of volunteers to participate as members of the study sample. This group was used to assist the researcher in verifying the accuracy of the research data collection methods.

3.4 Methods of analysis

The coded data was classified into different themes to be critically interpreted, and discussed. In developing themes from the data collected, the researcher studied the prominent consistent elements of themes and sub themes and critically assessed the level of variation within each emerging theme. Additionally, data collected through in-depth interviews, focus group discussions, documentary reviews, and records were utilized to validate and confirm the identified themes that align with the research objectives. Thematic analysis was used to process qualitative data that were presented in narrative forms through words, pictures, and symbols. When analyzing the documents, a critical examination of the available records was conducted, both official and non-official records

about the study carefully scrutinized to provide valuable descriptive information about the heads of secondary schools and teenage mothers.

4. PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

4.1 Heads of schools' experiences in managing teenage mothers in their secondary schools

Heads of secondary schools often face different situations when managing teenage mothers in their secondary schools. They need to create an inclusive and supportive environment that addresses the unique needs of these young mothers as they continue with their education. Heads of such schools should further ensure these young mothers, successfully complete and pass their secondary school cycle. In this way the goal of educating each of the Tanzania's national population can be met as well as ensuring that those who qualify to enter higher education can join college and university level institutions. These are basic conditions for youths' earning employment and decent livelihoods for Tanzanians after graduation from schools and higher learning institutions.

Heads of schools who participated in this study reported that they had some experiences in managing ordinary students and their schools' staff. However, they did not have sufficient experiences in managing schooling teenage mothers in their schools. Hence, they managed teenage mothers enrolled in their schools on the basis of their own lived experiences as teachers, leaders in secondary schools and parents. Hence, during the interview the heads of schools expressed their perceptions grounded on their personal experiences since they were not trained at any time along their leadership positions. The head teacher at Meru secondary school informed the researchers the following;

“The policy of admitting and retaining teenage mothers in secondary schools is relatively new for most school heads. Currently, we manage these students using our personal experiences, applying a combination of approaches for "ordinary students" and "teenage mothers." Some of these students have already enrolled or transferred into schools initiated for this purpose. To effectively support students who become teenage mothers while in school, we need training to gain the necessary knowledge and skills. Previously, many school heads believed that if secondary school girls became pregnant, they had to be expelled. However, as secondary school rules and regulations have changed, we now must abide by government policies that require us to keep these students in school. Overall, most secondary school heads have not received training on how to implement the new policy. We have only received circulars from the Ministry of

Education instructing us to retain and re-admit teenage mothers. The practice of accommodating teenage mothers in regular secondary schools remains perplexing for us.”

The responses cited above imply that the education policy that allows teenage mothers to continue with studies at secondary schools was disseminated to schools without being comprehensively and critically explored for the heads of secondary schools to comprehend and interpret implications on the management of their schools. For any policy to be adequately accommodated and effectively practiced, institutional managers, other school employees and communities ought to be made practically aware of the policy and ensuing implications to school management and other institutional members. In this case, even the teenage mothers, their parents or guardians and communities surrounding the schools should have been exposed to the policy prior to practicing the policy in the schools.

Given that prior to the new policy allowing teenage mothers to continue with secondary school education after getting pregnant and delivering their babies, most of the country's population including heads of secondary schools, schools' management teams, teaching-and-non-teaching staff, 'Secondary Schools' Board Members' and majority of the Tanzanian's population were accustomed to the practices of total expulsion of teenage mothers from their secondary schools' studies. Therefore, there was an urgent need for MoEST to ensure all members of the Tanzanian population get exposed to the new secondary education policy changes which allow secondary schools to enroll teenage mothers in secondary schools. All secondary schools' stakeholders should have been trained, or at least be made aware of the new policy changes before it was officially implemented. Since most of secondary schools' stakeholders were not systematically trained or made aware through a variety of techniques to clearly conceptualize the changes and the way such changes ought to be implemented, old beliefs and practices of expelling teenage mothers, haunts heads of secondary schools to date.

Some of them still believe that if secondary schools teenage students get pregnant while at school, they are supposed to be expelled from schools. Under these conditions, the current policy of letting teenage mothers continue with their studies in secondary schools, as well as their re-admission after they deliver their children remains a kind of a nightmare to some of the heads of secondary schools. On this basis, some teenage mothers, do study under school environments where there are no satisfactory or highly constrained management and learning environments for heads of secondary schools, teaching and non-teaching staff as well as the teenage mothers themselves. Therefore, the need for MEST to ensure that heads of schools and other secondary schools' stake holders are made aware through training for the acquisition of knowledge, skills and values needed to effectively and efficiently management and the education and sustainability of teenage mothers' interests and school success.

The following are more voices from heads of secondary schools responded to exemplify the need for their training in the area of managing teenage mothers in secondary schools in Tanzania's secondary schools. The head of Atlas secondary school stated;

As a secondary school head, I have never received any formal training to gain the knowledge and skills needed to effectively manage young mothers in my school. While seminars are often organized for school coordinators and subject teachers to build relevant competencies, those responsible seem to overlook the critical role of school heads as the ultimate authorities responsible for all teaching, learning, and operational aspects of the institution. If any challenges arise for the teenage mothers enrolled, it will ultimately fall on the school head to address them, despite the specific responsibilities of education coordinators and teachers. The current approach of excluding school heads from the capacity-building process is a significant oversight, as we are the ones who must navigate and implement the policies around supporting student mothers within the school context.

The statement from the head of secondary school provides a critical perspective on the essential prerequisites for the effective management of teenage mothers in educational institutions. The response underscores the pivotal role of training, knowledge, and skills as key and crucial elements in successfully supporting and accommodating teenage mothers within the secondary school context in Tanzania.

4.2 Strategies employed by heads of schools in managing and supporting teenage mothers in secondary schools

Heads of schools played a crucial role in managing and supporting teenage mothers in secondary schools, such young mothers often faced unique challenges such as balancing their academic responsibilities with the demands of motherhood. The demands included among others study and references text, food, child support. To effectively address these issues, heads of secondary schools have so far implemented various strategies which ensure the well-being and success of teenage mothers through their study track. The strategies have been stated to include among others: provision of parenting and life skills to teenage mothers, collaborating with communities, specifically parents and other interested education stake holders to provide supportive guidance and counseling services, academic support for teenage mothers when they miss classes due to their engagement in providing necessary childcare services including attending scheduled children's clinic visits, allowing teenage mothers to come into classes with their children

when children's care taker(s) had not attended the children due to unavoidable reasons, and provision of funds to support both teenage mothers and their toddlers.

4.2.1 Parenting and life skills education

Parenting and life skills education can be valuable strategies employed by heads of schools in managing teenage mothers. By incorporating these elements into schools' extra curriculum.

The head of Uluguru secondary school in Kinondoni District provided the researcher with the following information:

As a head of school, I always work with 'life skills curriculum' teachers, and other teachers as well so as to integrate parenting and life skills topic in our classes. I do this because these skills cover different and very important topics such as positive discipline, child development, and healthy parenting practices. These topics are likely to provide teenage mothers with practical parenting skills, and life skills. If effectively taught, the teachers assist teenage mothers to feel confident and competent in their role as parents as well as students.

The response above, highlights the critical role that life skills education can play in empowering teenage mothers with the necessary knowledge and abilities to effectively care for and raise their children. This perspective underscores the multifaceted nature of the support required to address the unique needs of this vulnerable student population.

From the life skills teacher at Rungwe secondary school in Ubungo District had the following to say during our interview session:

As a life skills teacher, I make time to meet with the young mothers and help them develop the skills needed for independent living. I guide them on managing daily tasks, effective social interactions, personal care, and job skills. Importantly, I encourage them to trust and value themselves, not see themselves as weak, and stay focused on their educational goals. I also advise them not to isolate themselves, but rather reach out to peers, teachers, the head of school, or other trusted community members when facing challenges, and seek assistance as needed.

Based on the responses from the respondents presented above, it becomes clear that the objectives of parenting and life skills programs for teenage mothers in secondary school

education in Tanzania specifically in Dar es salaam Region supports the development of knowledge and skills, as well as empower teenage mothers' capacity to overcome the obstacles they encounter. They develop interpersonal abilities that can support them in developing coping mechanisms, self-management techniques, and making informed decisions. They are also made aware on the need for assuring they have good communication skills and confidence; all these has the potential to contribute to their happy and fulfilling existences.

4.2.3 Collaboration with community members, parents and other education stake holders

Whenever it comes to handling teenage mothers in secondary education, school administrators may require support from the schools' communities, parents and other stakeholders. Despite the fact that, the communities, parents and other education stakeholders may exert pressure on schools to dismiss pregnant /parenting teenage students due to the challenges that heads of schools in schools that enroll teenage mothers encounter as they work out for appropriate strategies to address the teenage mothers' complicated schooling conditions and supporting the young teenage mothers along their education progress.

The following voice from head of school at Uluguru secondary school exemplifies the situation as the following;

Parents, guardian, and community involvement are essential for the holistic development of our teenage mother students, both intellectually and socially. We cannot effectively manage and support these young women without the cooperation of their families and the broader community. As a school, we make every effort to involve parents/guardians and community members, such as through regular meetings and phone communications, to address any challenges faced by the teenage mothers in our care.

Based on the response from the respondent's shows, that collaboration among heads of school, parents, and guardians may establish regular communication channels between parents, guardians, and teachers and provide opportunities for parents and guardians to attend school events and receiving training concerning with teenage mothers, this collaboration fosters a supportive environment that facilitates long-term success.

4.3 The challenges that heads of secondary schools' encounter in addressing the challenges teenage mothers encounter in the secondary schools

This section presents the findings on the challenge that heads of secondary school's encounter during the processes of managing teenage mothers in their school's context

within Dar es Salaam Region. The section also presents findings regarding how the challenges encountered are addressed.

The challenges that head of secondary schools' encounter in managing teenage mother in school contexts within Dar es Salaam Region range from personal, facilities and material support, teachers and community-level challenges. The heads of schools were asked to present the challenges they experience as they manage teenage mothers in their school contexts. The findings are presented between sections 4.3.1 and 4.3.4.

4.3.1 Teaching and learning infrastructure for serving teenage mothers' essential needs

Heads of the secondary schools, Secondary Schools' Coordinators, teachers and the teenage mothers reported that lack of teaching and learning infrastructure constituted one of the most disturbing challenges. The following voices exemplified the situations for the schools in the selected region for the study, i.e., Dar es Salaam Region.

The head of Kilimanjaro secondary school informed the researcher in the following words:

While the policy allowing teenage mothers in secondary schools is a positive step, it remains inadequate. Providing educational access is necessary but insufficient, as it fails to address the distinct infrastructural and resource needs of this marginalized group. There is a lack of tailored teaching and learning materials, forcing teenage mothers to rely on resources intended for "ordinary" students, highlighting the need for equity-driven investments. Beyond just access, the policy must be accompanied by specialized infrastructure, facilities, and resources designed to enhance the learning experience and well-being of teenage mothers, such as childcare services, flexible scheduling, and counseling support. A holistic approach is necessary to ensure the promise of educational opportunities is matched by the requisite support systems to facilitate their meaningful and equitable participation.

The dearth of adequate teaching and learning materials can severely impede the ability of teenage mothers to effectively comprehend and engage with the academic curriculum. Without access to the necessary resources, such as textbooks, learning aids, and technology-enabled tools, these students may struggle to keep pace with their peers and experience difficulties in mastering the required content and skills. This lack of access to fundamental educational resources can undermine the learning process and contribute to widening achievement gaps between teenage mothers and other student populations.

Moreover, the limited availability of opportunities for extracurricular activities, such as sports, arts, and cultural programs, can deprive teenage mothers of the holistic development experiences that are essential for their overall well-being and personal growth. Participation in these activities not only fosters important social-emotional skills but also provides a valuable avenue for teenage mothers to explore their interests, build a sense of community, and nurture their self-confidence. The absence of these enrichment opportunities can further marginalize teenage mothers and constrain their ability to thrive both academically and personally. Addressing these challenges requires a concerted effort by educational institutions to invest in the provision of high-quality teaching and learning resources, as well as the creation of diverse extracurricular offerings tailored to the needs and preferences of teenage mothers. By ensuring equitable access to essential educational materials and a wide range of developmental activities, schools can empower these students to fully engage with the learning process, cultivate their talents and interests, and ultimately achieve their academic and personal goals.

Another opinion from a teacher at Atlas secondary school is expressed below:

It's true that in order to achieve good academic success we need teaching and learning facilities as well as stationary materials in order to attempt our daily and weekly exercises which are likely to build our learners 'academic excellence. Actually, there has been a shortage of teaching and learning infrastructure and materials for teenage mothers such as classrooms, and laboratory equipment for practical training.

The information provided in the previous responses highlights several key challenges that school heads enrolling teenage mothers may encounter, particularly related to the availability and state of teaching and learning infrastructure and facilities. These challenges can indeed be considered among the major obstacles for the effective management of teenage mothers in secondary schools within the Dar-es-Salaam region. Firstly, the lack of adequate teaching and learning resources, such as textbooks, learning aids, and technology-enabled tools, can significantly hinder the ability of teenage mothers to engage with and comprehend the academic curriculum. Without access to these fundamental educational materials, these students may struggle to keep up with their peers and experience difficulties in mastering the required content and skills. Secondly, the limited opportunities for extracurricular activities, including sports, arts, and cultural programs, can deprive teenage mothers of valuable avenues for holistic development. Participation in these enrichment activities not only fosters important social-emotional skills but also provides a means for these students to explore their interests, build a sense of community, and nurture their self-confidence.

4.3.2 Teachers and students' perceptions about teenage mothers in secondary schools

Depending on personal views, attitudes, and experiences, secondary school teachers', and students, perceptions of teenage mothers can differ. But it's crucial to remember that prejudices, cultural origins, and society conventions can all have an impact on how people perceive things. Head of school from Atlas secondary school in Kigamboni district said the following during his interview:

At the beginning of this policy regarding the issue of teenage mothers, some teachers and students have revealed different opinions from the implementers of the policy. Teachers are typically dissatisfied and unprepared to assist teenage mothers and girls who are pregnant in secondary schools. They think that teaching is their line of work and not practicing midwifery. The teachers in my school always complain that students should attend school and those teenagers who get pregnant at our school should be expelled and go home to take care of their children and the family that they have initiated in an untimely manner.

The response above provided has powerfully illuminated the profound impact that negative perceptions and biases surrounding teenage mothers can have on their educational experiences and long-term trajectories. These deeply entrenched societal attitudes, which often permeate the secondary school context, can erect formidable barriers that obstruct the academic progress, emotional well-being, and future prospects of this vulnerable student population.

At the same school, the school coordinator informed the researcher that some teachers and students perceive teenage mothers like bad example. The coordinator commented the following:

When the policy was first implemented, we faced a lot of challenges concerning teenage mothers, many students perceived the young mothers as scallywags and undisciplined. Some teachers were also not comfortable with accepting teenage mothers in secondary schools; hence we had to use stringent punishment for any teacher who harassed the teenage mother. In response to the situation, the school planned and executed an in-house training program to generate awareness for the teachers on how positively handle teenage mother at our school.

The information provided suggests that both teachers and fellow students may hold lower expectations for the academic performance and future success of teenage mothers. This dynamic of low expectations can lead to a self-fulfilling prophecy, whereby the perceived limitations of teenage mothers become a reality due to the lack of encouragement, support, and opportunities afforded to them. Such an environment can severely undermine the aspirations and achievements of these students, depriving them of the chance to reach their full potential. Furthermore, the combination of societal stigma, inadequate institutional support, potential bullying from peers, and the prevalence of low expectations can significantly contribute to higher dropout rates among teenage mothers.

4.3.3 Training

Lack of training for staff members, teachers, as well as heads of school working with teenage mothers can also lead to ineffective support and guidance. Proper training is essential to equip educators and staff with the necessary skills and knowledge to address the unique challenges faced by teenage mothers, such as balancing schoolwork with parenting responsibilities, accessing resources for childcare, and managing social and emotional well-being.

The following is the voice from head of school from Atlas secondary school found in Kigamboni exemplifying the situation:

As a head of secondary school, I have not received any formal training to gain the knowledge and skills needed for effectively managing young mothers in my school. However, school coordinators and some subject teachers often attend seminars to build relevant expertise. It appears that the organizers of these seminars overlook the fact that secondary school heads are responsible for the overall management of teaching, learning, and work conditions for both teachers and students. Therefore, if any challenges arise for the teenage mothers, it would be the head teacher's responsibility to address them, as the education coordinators and teachers have their own specific duties and do not manage the students or the school environment.

The findings from the responses have brought to light a critical shortcoming in the preparedness of secondary school heads to effectively support and address the unique needs of teenage mothers within the educational system. Without the necessary training and capacity-building initiatives, school administrators may struggle to provide the comprehensive support and resources required for these vulnerable students to thrive both academically and personally. Investing in the professional development of school

heads is crucial, as it equips them with a deeper understanding of the multifaceted challenges faced by teenage mothers. Targeted training programs can enable school heads to create a more supportive and inclusive environment, wherein they can leverage appropriate policies and collaborate with a range of stakeholders, including teachers, counselors, and community resources, to holistically address the needs of this student population.

4.3.4 Motivation for teachers

In order to manage teenage mothers in a school setting effectively, motivation can be a very useful tool, but most of the teachers who taught for teenage mothers are faced with great challenge of poor motivation.

The following voice from head of Kilimanjaro secondary school in Ilala District exemplifying the situation:

Most of the heads of schools we are not recognized as main people who ensuring these young mothers are in a good teaching and learning environment, dealing with behavior issue, challenging parents or guardians of these young mothers but there is no any allowance provided by government, not only allowance but also even training, poor teaching and learning infrastructures.

The finding above has illuminated a concerning issue regarding the lack of recognition and support for secondary heads school in their pivotal role of overseeing the educational experiences of teenage mothers. This critical gap within the educational system can lead to significant challenges in maintaining discipline, implementing effective policies, and cultivating a structured and nurturing environment for this vulnerable student population. School heads occupy a unique position at the intersection of institutional leadership, policy implementation, and student support. As the primary architects of a school's culture and climate, their ability to prioritize and address the needs of teenage mothers is paramount. However, the findings suggest that the absence of appropriate recognition and institutional backing for school heads can undermine their capacity to fulfill this vital function effectively.

Without a strong sense of validation and empowerment, school heads may struggle to assert their authority and maintain discipline within the school setting. This can lead to a breakdown in the enforcement of policies and protocols designed to support teenage mothers, ultimately compromising the safety, stability, and academic progress of these students. Furthermore, the lack of recognition for school heads can also impede their ability to spearhead the implementation of tailored policies and programs that cater to the specific needs of teenage mothers. These students often require a comprehensive suite of academic, social, and emotional support services that necessitate the dedicated coordination and advocacy of school leadership. When heads feel unsupported or

undervalued, they may be less inclined to champion and sustain these critical interventions.

5. CONCLUSION

The research presents compelling findings that highlight the significant challenges faced by head of school in managing the needs of teenage mothers in secondary schools in the Dar es Salaam region. The study illuminates several critical barriers, including low teacher motivation, financial constraints, and unfavorable attitudes among both teachers and students. These complex issues underscore the lack of experience and preparedness among school heads in supporting this vulnerable student population. The findings make it clear that a more holistic and targeted approach is necessary to address the unique needs of teenage mothers in the education system. School heads play a pivotal role in fostering a supportive and inclusive environment where these young women can thrive both academically and emotionally. Strategies such as providing comprehensive support services, flexible scheduling, and mentorship programs are crucial in enabling teenage mothers to manage their dual responsibilities of parenting and education.

5.1 Recommendations

- i. There is need for compulsory in-service-training and professional development: Heads and teachers in secondary schools which enroll teenage mothers need to go through thorough short and/or long-term training sessions focused on provision knowledge and skills that the in-service-trainees need to effectively deal /serve teenage mother who study in their secondary schools. The trainees also need training on guidance and counseling so that they get enabled to offer emotional support for teenage mothers, foster inclusive school settings, and attend to educational needs of the adolescent mothers who pursue studies in schools.
- ii. There is need for resource allocation to schools that enroll teenage mothers: It is necessary to make an urgent case for supplying sufficient financing, teaching and learning resources that guarantee that schools with teenage mothers enrolled have the instructional resources they require. Such supply guarantees the potential to improve the standards of instruction given both to teenage mothers and other categories of students in secondary schools.

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